

Catalytic oxidation of sulphides using polymer anchored cobalt complex

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Manuscript received 27 July 2009, accepted 12 April 2010

Abstract : Polymer-anchored cobalt complex was synthesised by supporting it on cation exchange resin (polystyrene). The catalyst was characterized by some physicochemical techniques. It was found to be active for oxidation of sulphides under mild conditions of temperature and pressure, with molecular oxygen as the oxidant.

Keywords : Polymer-anchored catalyst, oxidation, molecular oxygen, swelling.

Introduction

Polymer-anchored metal complexes are immobilized reagents which can be considered as heterogenised homogeneous catalysts. They find solution to many practical problems including the recovery of the catalyst from the reaction mixture and its reuse^{1,2}. Further they can be made more selective and specific by varying the porosity of the polymer backbone or by choice of a suitable solvent for the reaction³. The oxidation of sulphides to sulphoxides has been extensively studied because of the importance of sulphoxides as useful intermediate in organic synthesis⁴ and their key role in the activation of enzymes⁵. The present work describes the oxidation of sulphides using polymer-anchored cobalt complex with molecular oxygen as the oxidant.

Results and discussion

The catalyst (cobalt complex supported on cation exchange resin) was prepared by anchoring cobalt chloride on Stryrem-DVB 225 resin and characterized by elemental analysis, SEM and IR spectroscopy⁶.

The insoluble catalyst shows affinity for solvents and the solvent retaining capacity of the catalyst is expressed in terms of equilibrium solvent content (ESC).

The ESC values calculated for some solvents are reported in the Table 1.

Maximum swelling is obtained in water and methanol for the catalyst. Methanol was chosen as the solvent for the reactions, because of the better swelling and miscibility with the substrates.

Table 1. Swelling studies of polymer-metal complex

Sl. no.	Solvent	Wet weight (g)	Dry weight (g)	ESC (%)
1.	Water	0.689	0.449	34.8
2.	Methanol	0.631	0.446	29.5
3.	Dioxane	0.586	0.458	25.4
4.	Benzene	0.551	0.436	21.8

Dimethyl sulphide and diphenyl sulphide were taken as the substrates for oxidation; the rates of reaction are ($\times 10^3 \text{ Mm}^{-1}$) 0.83 and 0.75 respectively ([catalyst] $\times 10^3 = 0.590 \text{ M}$, temp. 35 °C).

Dimethyl sulphide shows a higher rate of reaction because of the inductive effect of two methyl groups. The electrophilic attack of oxygen on the sulphur atom becomes more facile. The relatively smaller size of the methyl group makes it easier to enter into the polymer matrix, than for the bulkier phenyl groups. In case of both the substrates the rate of oxidation increases linearly on increasing the concentrations of both the catalyst and the substrate, showing a first order dependence on their concentrations.

Product analysis :

Dimethyl sulphide has been used as a substrate for oxidation by several workers using various oxidants. All of them have reported dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) as the only product. In catalytic oxidation also DMSO has been reported as the product. So in the present study also we expect DMSO as the product. A qualitative study was done using TLC and UV-Visible spectroscopy for prod-

uct analysis. In both the studies DMSO was found to be the product by comparing the product with authentic sample. A mechanism proposed is :

The oxidation state of cobalt may be changing during the course of reaction as observed earlier⁷.

Experimental

All the solvents were purified by standard methods. AnalaR sample of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ supplied by Fischer was used as such. Styrene DVB 225 resin (cation exchange resin) was supplied by Ion Exchange India Ltd. Commercial oxygen was purified by passing through copper gauze maintained at 250 °C and dried over molecular sieve.

In the case of swelling studies, to find the ESC a fixed quantity of the catalyst is agitated in 50 ml of the solvent for 24 h. Afterwards the catalyst is filtered off and the solvent adhered on the surface is removed using tissue

paper. The catalyst is kept in vacuum desiccator for 24 h. Then the catalyst is weighed and dried in air oven at 110 ± 2 °C for constant weight.

$$\text{ESC} = \frac{\text{Weight of wet catalyst} - \text{weight of dry catalyst}}{\text{Weight of wet catalyst}} \times 100$$

Oxidation reactions were carried out at room temperature in a static reactor using molecular oxygen as the oxidant at one atmospheric pressure. The progress of reaction was followed by the uptake of oxygen using a gas burette. Blank experiments were carried out in the absence of catalyst and the substrate as well. In both the cases the reaction did not proceed.

Conclusion :

The polymer-anchored cobalt complex is found to be an efficient catalyst for the oxidation of sulphides under mild conditions of temperature and pressure.

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